

Briefing Pack

Dear colleagues,

This is our briefing pack for you. You will find all the information and templates you will need to administer the interviews and communicate with the experts in your country. The briefing pack includes FAQs on the *process* in general and on the interview itself, as well as templates and checklists to support you. Please feel free to modify the templates as you see fit.

What is the goal of WP2?

The main goal of WP2 will be to analyse the development and implementation of legal provisions and policy frameworks that protect and support adolescent young carers (AYCs) and their families in six selected European countries.

In order to do this, we need to understand the broader picture and therefore explore legislation and policy frameworks which are relevant to young carers of all ages.

Specific aims of the research:

1) To examine what legal provisions and other policy frameworks exist in six selected European countries (Italy, Netherlands, Slovenia, Sweden, Switzerland and UK) that provide support and protection for young carers. Such provisions may be laws and guidance that are specifically directed at young carers, or they may be legislation and guidance that applies to all vulnerable children and which can be used to protect and support young carers and their families.

2) To explore how such policies are translated into practice.

Young carers: *'Young carers' are children who provide care for another person (normally for other family members). They often assume significant responsibility for care on a regular basis. This responsibility is something normally associated with adults. The person needing care is usually a parent. However, it may also be a sibling, a grandparent or another relative with a physical, mental or cognitive health issue.*

Age range: *We are interested in legal provisions and policy frameworks that support young carers up to 25 years old.*

Notes:

- A young person caring for someone with an addiction can also be a 'young carer'.
- The target group for the ME-WE project are Adolescent Young Carers (AYCs), between 15 and 17 years of age. In order to provide the context for reporting on the legal, policy and service frameworks for the target group, we are interested in legal provisions and policy frameworks that support young carers and young adult carers (or AYCs) up to 25 years old.
- We are also interested in legal and policy provisions for young people caring for another person, who may not be a family member or in the same household.

Expert interviews

In order to gain information about the legal and policy context in the different countries, experts with a deep understanding of the legal provisions in each country will be interviewed. The interview guidelines were developed for this purpose and one former young carer was involved in their development.

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Appendix 1: FAQ about the process

How do I recruit experts? Are there any materials to help me?

You have received the list of experts from us, which has been agreed upon. You also have within this pack:

Appendix 5: Template 1 Email to send along with the Invitation Letter

Appendix 6: Invitation Letter for experts

Please contact the experts if you have not already done so, using the template email (Appendix 5) (modified if you would like) and the Invitation Letter (Appendix 6). Please contact the experts in the order that they are prioritised on the list.

What should I do if someone does not respond, or does not wish to participate?

Please use Appendix 9 ('Recruitment log') to note your contact activity. If someone does not respond after 7 days, please remind them that you would like to interview them and how important they are as an expert for our H2020 project. If after a further 10 days there is no response, please start to work down the reserve list of experts – in order. Please inform us, if you have to contact the reserve experts or if you encounter any problems in fixing interviews. We will seek to help you find a solution.

If you are experiencing serious recruitment problems, please do not hesitate to contact us by emailing: xxx.

What should I send to an expert once they agree to participate in an interview?

Please use Template email (Appendix 7) - please modify and use this as appropriate. However, please do not change the wording of the questions which are included in this template email.

Please also include the Consent Form (Appendix 3)

Which technology can I use to conduct the interview?

Interviews can be carried out on the phone or preferably by Skype (or equivalent). You are free to choose the best option for yourself and the interviewee.

Do the interviews and materials need to be translated?

No, there is no need if you are able to carry these out in English. We strongly recommend that the interviews are conducted in English where possible, otherwise the materials will need to be translated into English before the interview and then the transcript would be needed to be translated into English for us. There is no extra budget for translations.

Please let us know at SKF, if you intend to translate the Interview Schedule or other materials (e.g. Consent Form; Invitation Letter).

How many interviews will I need to undertake?

- Each country (apart from the UK) has 4 expert interviews to conduct. The UK (who have 6 person months for WP2) will have 5 expert interviews.

When should I start and finish my interviews by?

- The whole interview process will start from **30th April 2018** and run until the **end of July 2018**. August 2018 is a contingency period in case the recruitment process does not work as planned. We would like to advise that if you have not already arranged the first interview with an expert in your country, that this initial interview is arranged with an expert in law (rather than in policy or research for example). By interviewing those whose expertise lies primarily within the legal world, this should lead to the most comprehensive responses and should therefore be most informative with respect to modifications for the subsequent interviews.
- The **first interview** should be completed, transcribed, translated (if appropriate) and sent to us by **20th May 2018**, so that we can do a quick analysis and provide partners with feedback by 8th June 2018. From 9th June to 31st July 2018, you are free to carry out the remaining 3 interviews (4 in the UK).

How should the interviews be transcribed?

- Please undertake a full transcription of the interview.

What should I send to SKF and how?

- Please send us your (a) transcript, (b) audio file of the interview and (c) your scanned notes from the interview. To ensure data security, please do not send this by email. Instead, please use our online storage “Box” for the Me-We project and just inform us by email that you uploaded it.

When do I send back the remaining interviews to SKF?

- Please send back the remaining 3 interviews (4 in UK), as soon as each interview has been transcribed and translated (if appropriate) rather than sending them all together after the final interview has taken place.
- All transcribed interviews need to have been returned to SKF by the very latest 31st August
- Please refer to ‘Checklist of what to return to SKF’ (included in Appendix 2)

Appendix 2: FAQ about the interview itself

Since we would like to explore a topic that we know little about, but which has a specific focus on legal provisions and policy frameworks, we will use interview guidelines that based on a semi-structured, step-by-step approach and which contains 8 ‘question blocks’.

The approach for each ‘question block’ is to get participants to answer very focused initial questions (the “Main Question”). After that, the use of prompts will seek deeper understanding, before encouraging wider responses by asking participants whether they have anything to add at the end of each block.

Although it is important that the interview covers all the main questions, please feel free to expand the expert interview if there is time by asking if the experts have anything to add at the end of each block. You are also free to change the order of the questions. If the expert starts discussing something out of order, for example, future hopes and goals at the beginning, you allow them to discuss this and simply mark the question as answered. However, when you come to that question later on it is worth recapping briefly what has been discussed and using the question at the end of each block ‘Is there anything else you would like add about...’

Language and translation of the interview schedule

We strongly recommend that the interviews are conducted in English where possible

If you need to translate the interview guidelines and any other material (e.g. contact email, letters for experts, etc.) please be mindful of the key dates for returning the first transcription to us (20th May) and be aware that there is no extra budget for this work.

What should I do before the interview? (Checklist)

- Please print out your interview guidelines before the interview. Any hand-written notes you take should be scanned and returned to us after the interview.
- Please make sure that you have a professional audio recording device with high sound quality. Please also have additional batteries in reserve to ensure your device has sufficient power for the interview.
- Please remember to make sure that you are in a quiet environment because any background noise will be picked up by the recording device very clearly on your audio file – we just highly recommend this because we will have a wide range of different accents to understand and so this will make things easier for us 😊.

What are we interested in?

- National, regional and local (or equivalent) legal provisions and policy frameworks (both current and historical) that provide protection and support for young carers and their families
- Specific and non-specific legal provisions and policy frameworks (both current and historical) that benefit young carers aged 0-24

What are we not interested in?

- Practice guidelines
- Advice and resources for supporting young carers

How long should the interview be and in which language should they be undertaken?

- Duration of the interview should not take longer than an hour. However, please be aware that the interview could take slightly longer depending on the English skills of the participant, if the interview is conducted in English.

At the end of the interview...

- Please ask if you can contact the expert later if you have any further questions (to clarify any points).
- Please fill out the summary sheet which you will find at the end of the interview guidelines.

	Checklist of what to return to SKF	✓
1	Transcription of interview (translated into English if necessary)	
2	The audio-file of interview	
2	Summary Sheet (At the end of the Interview Guidelines)	
3	Your scanned handwritten notes (If you have taken any)	
4	Feedback Form - Appendix 4 (After interview 1 only)	
5	Recruitment log – Appendix 9 (After all interviews are done)	

Appendix 3: Consent form

I have read and understood the information about the content of the expert interview – this includes the main topics for the interview that were sent to me beforehand, as well as the information letter.

I understand that I will be recognised as an expert in the report, but that anything I say will not be linked to my name.

On this basis, I consent to take part in the study and I give my consent for material from my contribution being used for the purposes of the report, research and publication.

I understand that I can withdraw from the research at any stage.

I also understand that all my contributions (including the audio file) will be stored in a locked filing cabinet, and ten years after the project is completed, these will be shredded and the audio files deleted.

Name of Interviewer: _____ Organisation: _____

Your name: _____ Date: _____

Signature: _____

Appendix 4: Feedback form after interview 1

After undertaking the first (only) interview, transcription (and translation - if required), please return this **Feedback Form** to SKF along with the transcribed interview by **May 20th**.

Please list any issues that you have encountered with the interview itself, as well as with the process in general.

We will consider the feedback from all partners and adjust the interview guidelines and the process according to your comments. Any modifications will be communicated by the **8th June**. After that, you may undertake the remaining interviews.

Feedback Form Template

Question / prompt	Specific point	Suggested change
E.g. Question 1a	This question is too...	Please.....

Appendix 5: Template 1 email to send along with the invitation letter (Appendix 6) (To modify)

Dear Sir/Madam,

This letter is being sent to you on behalf of the European H2020 ME-WE project. We have identified you as an expert in the field of either young carers, family caregiving or children's rights and we would like to invite you to participate in an 'Expert Interview'. Me-We (abbreviation for Psychosocial Support for Promoting **M**ental health and **W**ellbeing among adolescent young carers in Europe) aims to **strengthen the resilience of adolescent young carers**, in order to impact positively on their mental health and wellbeing and to mitigate the negative influences of psychosocial and environmental factors.

For your information, we have attached an 'Invitation Letter' providing details about these interviews. Your expertise would be extremely valuable to the ME-WE project and we would very much appreciate your participation.

The interviews will be carried out in English and take approximately one hour.

Best regards,

National Contact (country partner)

Appendix 6: Invitation letter for experts

ME-WE Legislation and Policy Frameworks

Subject: Expert interviews

Date:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 754702"

Dear Sir/Madam,

We are writing to you on behalf of the European H2020 ME-WE project, as we have identified you as being an expert in legislation and policy in the field of adolescent young carers.

Background

The overall goal of the ME-WE project is to strengthen the resilience of adolescent young carers (AYCs) in transition to adulthood (15-17 years old) in order to impact positively on their mental health and well-being and to mitigate the negative influence of psychosocial and environmental factors in their lives. The part of the project that is being led by SKF (Careum Research, Research Department of Kalaidos University of Applied Sciences, Department Health) aims to find out more about legal provisions and policy frameworks that provide support and protection for adolescent young carers in six European countries (Italy, Netherlands, Sweden, Switzerland, Slovenia and the UK). Furthermore, we will explore how such policies are enacted in the 'real' world.

Expert Interviews

We will be undertaking a total of 24 'Expert Interviews', four in each of the six countries. Each semi-structured interview will gather the opinions of experts about specific and non-specific legislation that exists in each country to protect young carers, how provisions are enacted in practice and about the strengths and limitations of these provisions. Interviews will also explore how changes in policy were achieved and what are the goals and hopes for the future, in relation to provisions for young carers.

The one-hour interviews will be carried out in person, by Skype or telephone as appropriate, and will be transcribed and analysed. They are planned to take place between April and August, 2018. Where possible, interviews will be carried out in English (please confirm whether this will be suitable).

We would greatly appreciate your participation in one of these important interviews. Your contribution will enhance our understanding of legal provisions and policy frameworks that is vital for underpinning this important project which in turn will improve support for adolescent young carers across Europe. The findings of the interviews will be written up into an internal report to provide context and to underpin the project as a whole.

Please let us know whether you would be happy to participate. You are also more than welcome to suggest other experts in the field who might be willing to be interviewed.

If you have any questions please do not hesitate to contact us.

Best Regards,

[NAME] [SIGNATURE] on behalf of country lead

Address:

[EMAIL]

[ORGANIZATION]

[STREET...]

www.me-we.eu

Appendix 7: Template 2 email - once experts have accepted (to modify)

Dear ...

Thank you for your willingness to support the European H2020 ME-WE project by participating in an 'Expert Interview'. Your expertise in legislation and policy, in the field of either young carers, family caregiving or children's rights will help us in enhancing our understanding about legal provisions and policy frameworks that can provide support and protection for adolescent young carers in six European countries (Italy, Netherlands, Sweden, Switzerland, Slovenia and the UK).

Young carers: 'Young carers' are children who provide care for another person (normally for other family members). They often assume significant responsibility for care on a regular basis. This responsibility is something normally associated with adults. The person needing care is usually a parent. However, it may also be a sibling, a grandparent or another relative with a physical, mental or cognitive health issue.

Age range: We are interested in legal provisions and policy frameworks that support young carers up to 25 years old.

Notes:

- A young person caring for someone with an addiction can also be a 'young carer'.
- The target group for the ME-WE project are Adolescent Young Carers (AYCs), between 15 and 17 years of age. In order to provide the context for reporting on the legal, policy and service frameworks for the target group, we are interested in legal provisions and policy frameworks that support young carers and young adult carers (or AYCs) up to 25 years old.
- We are also interested in legal and policy provisions for young people caring for another person, who may not be a family member or in the same household.

During a **1-hour interview**, the following questions will be posed:

- 1a. Is there any specific legislation to protect and support young carers and their families?
- 1b. Are there any specific policy and/or service frameworks to protect and support young carers and their families?
- 1c. How does the legislation define and construct young carers?
- 1d. How do the policy and/or service frameworks define and construct young carers?
- 2a. Is there any other (non-specific) legislation that can or has been used in the context of young carers and their families?
- 2b. Are there any other (non-specific) policy and/or service framework that can or has been used in the context of young carers and their families?
3. How do the legislation, policy and/or services frameworks translate into practice?

4. What are the key strengths of the legislation, policy and/or service frameworks? Are there any limitations of the legislation, policy and/or service frameworks?
5. How were any changes in legislation, policy and/or service frameworks achieved?
- 6a. How would you evaluate the current situation regarding the legislation, policy and/or service frameworks?
- 6b. Changes you would suggest?
7. What are your goals or hopes for the future with regards to the development of legislation, policy and/or service frameworks for young carers?

We greatly appreciate your participation in one of these important interviews.

For more information or questions, please contact **National Investigator (country partner)**.

Best regards,

[NAME] [SIGNATURE] on behalf of country lead

Address:

[EMAIL]

[ORGANISATION]

[STREET...]

www.me-we.eu

Appendix 8: Template “thank you” email to send after the interview

Dear Sir/Madam,

Thank you for participating to the European H2020 ME-WE project. The information that you provided us will be very helpful to enhance our understanding about legal provisions and policy frameworks existing in our country. This information will help us to develop a framework of primary prevention interventions that can provide support and protection for young carers.

In order to gain more knowledge about this topic, we would like to ask you if you know other experts in the field of either young carers, family caregiving or children’s rights. This would help us in gaining a broader understanding of the topic.

Thank you.

Best regards,

National contact (country partner)

Appendix 9: Recruitment Log

Country	Name of expert	Organisation of expert	Gender	Kind of expert	Date of contact	Date of interview	Interview type	Interview Language	Duration of Interview	Name of interviewer	Name of organisation of Interviewer	Transcribed	Notes
e.g. Sweden	Hans Muster	University of xx	male	law professor	yyyy.mm.dd	yyyy.mm.dd	Skype/telephone etc.	English	60'	Daniel	SFK	No or Yes	

